

Roadside checks in pig transport – inspection checklists and guidelines

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The aim of this report is to describe checklists and their guidelines used for roadside inspection of pig transport in EU MS's. This report is designed to support the work of inspectors and highlights the challenges that inspectors face during inspection where welfare can be challenging to assess. The focus is on journeys of >8 hours and thus vehicles approved as Type II.

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Contents

1	Summary	3
2	Introduction	3
3	Materials and Methods	3
4	Results	3
	4.1 The animals	5
	4.2 The means of transport.....	6
5	Conclusions	7
6	References.....	8
	About EURCAW-Pigs.....	10

1 Summary

The aim of this report is to describe checklists and their guidelines used for roadside inspection of pig transport in EU MS's. This report is designed to support the work of inspectors and highlights the challenges that inspectors face during inspection where welfare can be challenging to assess (see Mc Loughlin 2022). The focus is on journeys of >8 hours and thus vehicles approved as Type II.

2 Introduction

EU has a comprehensive legal framework to ensure consistent controls from farm to fork. This control should be risk based and efficient and it is up to MS's to determine a number of planned inspections per year, based on these requirements. From Article 9.1 of EU Regulation (2017/625), it is stated that competent authorities shall perform official controls on all operators regularly, on a risk basis and with appropriate frequency. Article 21.1 states that official controls to verify compliance with the rules shall be performed at all relevant stages of production, processing and distribution along the agri-food chain. Delegation of certain official control tasks to one or more persons are allowed. In relation to animal transport, the aim is to perform a uniform minimum frequency of such official controls, where a minimum level of official control is necessary to respond to the risk associated with different animal species and means of transport, and the need to prevent non-compliant practices and to limit the suffering of animals.

Across EU member states, animal transport can be inspected at several types of locations, e.g. at slaughterhouses, at departure from private farms, at assembly barns and also at control posts. In addition, animal welfare and means of transport can be inspected by so-called roadside checks, where competent authorities, often assisted by police or similar, can require that vehicles are stopped and then perform inspection.

3 Materials and Methods

This report is based on guidelines for road checks collected in selected EU MS's during the second half of 2023 and translated to English. It was not possible to retrieve the documents from all planned MS's because the guidelines were reported to be under revision. This report is based on guidelines from Denmark, Poland, France, and Ireland, as well as information from Denmark and Austria. Some countries have shared check lists as well as the associated guidelines. In addition, the German *Handbuch Tiertransporte* (Marschner et al., 2019), Gayer et al. (2015) and Rhode et al. (2023) have been used as supporting material.

4 Results

From the MS's where this information is available, roadside checks are typically performed by designated veterinarians assisted by the police (to stop traffic) or sometimes by the police alone. Road checks typically involve a team of police officers and veterinarians who are situated on a pull-up along a large road. All vehicles transporting animals are then pulled aside and checked (approximately 30 min per vehicle). This means that the specific vehicles are not chosen based on risk as such but can be considered a spot check and also that most checks are done during working hours.

According to Regulation 2017/625, each MS must provide a yearly plan for controls and has to report the controls as a yearly report, as described in the Implementation Regulation (2019/723), thereby ensuring harmonized reporting. Table 1 shows a copy of the reporting form. From the form, it is not possible to recognize whether the data come from roadside checks or other types of checks of animal transport (e.g. at control posts, slaughterhouses), but it might be mentioned in the covering letter.

It has not been possible to find information on the training of inspectors or the calibration of inspectors involved in roadside checks or between inspectors involved in roadside checks and inspectors for example involved in inspections at slaughterhouses, where vehicles as well as animals might also be inspected. However, this will be examined in a later study by EURCAW-Pigs.

6.4 Animal welfare during transport (Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 ⁽¹⁾)									
Protection of animals during transport (by species)	Number of official controls performed	Number and category of non-compliances						Actions/measures	
		1. Fitness of animals	2. Transport practices, space allowance, height	3. Means of transport	4. Water, feed, journey and resting times	5. Documents	6. Other	Administrative	Judicial
Bovine									
Porcine animals									
Ovine/caprine									
Equidae									
Poultry									
Other									

6.5 Analysis and action plan for animal welfare during transport

Figure 1. The table that MSs must use to report results of animal transport checks. Source: EU Regulation 2019/723.

In their textbook on animal transport, Gayer et al. (2015) describe that roadside checks are a challenge for everyone involved for a number of reasons (not in prioritized order): A) Depending on the density of animal transport in a given MS, the number of vehicles carrying animals can be quite low when standing near a road and waiting, and therefore the time used per inspected vehicle will include a lot of waiting time; B) Pull-up areas along larger roads are often of limited size which means that the checks should be done quickly in order not to block the space; C) Due to the presence of animals in the vehicles, time being stationary can be a challenge for the inter-vehicle build-up of heat and can also be a challenge in terms of biosecurity if more than one vehicle is present at the same time; D) the presence of other road users means that the working conditions for inspectors as well as livestock drivers can be challenged; E) It is not easy to inspect animals inside a vehicle and for example recognize lame animals or animals with hernia.

Table 2 shows a list of selected points of relevance for pig welfare that are checked during roadside inspections. Due to the limited available material for this report, the list may not be complete. Below, examples from the categories listed in the two columns from the left are discussed.

The animals	The means of transport	Documents
Not able to walk independently without pain	Sharp protrusions	A contingency plan
Sick/injured/weak animals	Not protected from weather	Certificate of competence
Open wounds/prolapses	Not cleaned/disinfected	Travel log
Gestation > 90%	Inadequate ventilation	
Parturition < 7 days ago	Not all animals can be accessed	
Navels not healed and wet	Inappropriate ramp angle	
Appropriate age (>10 kg)	Slippery flooring	
Sufficient head space	Inadequate bedding	
Number of animals	Not enough water in tank	
Weight of animals	Inappropriate drinkers	
Kg animals/m ² (over 235 kg)	Lack ventilation fans/functionality	
	Area per deck and in total	
	Temperature monitoring system	
	Navigation system	
	Temperatures within 5-30°C	

Table 2: List of selected points of relevance for pig welfare that are checked during roadside inspection of animal transport. The list is based on material from only few MSs and may not be complete.

4.1 The animals

As mentioned by Gayer et al. (2015), the fact that the animals are inside the vehicle at the time of inspection puts some limitations to what can be identified, such as animals being lame or animals with hernia. In cattle, identification of cows in a higher pregnancy stage than 90% is not possible with the required certainty, either from ante mortem inspection of the pregnant cow or from post mortem inspection of the calf fetus (Agerholm et al., 2023). Similar examinations have not been performed in pigs, but it is most likely not possible to identify the presence of a sow who is more than 90% into pregnancy by standing on a ladder and observing the animals through the ventilation openings (Figure 1), which is the only option to check the fitness for transport of the animals during roadside inspections.

Figure 2 Inspection of fitness for transport during roadside check by Danish police and veterinary authorities. In a 4-deck vehicle like on the picture, the deck height often is approximately 70 cm. Photo: Niels Arberg.

In the current EU Regulation (EC-1/2005) it is specified that the height provided for the animals should be appropriate for their size and for the intended journey. No quantitative thresholds are given, but it is stated that sufficient space shall be provided inside the animals' compartment and at each of its levels to ensure that there is adequate ventilation above the animals when they are in a naturally standing position, without on any account hindering their natural movement. In the recent scientific opinion from EFSA (EFSA AHAW Panel et al., 2022) on transport of pigs, the available research on vertical space in vehicles transporting pigs is reviewed and described as scarce. Thus, EFSA was not able to provide quantitative recommendations, but recommended research to establish evidence-based thresholds for vertical space, in order to prevent hazards such as reduced ventilation, lack of ability to move around and lack of space for natural movements, and thus avoid welfare consequences such as heat stress and restriction of movement. In the guidelines from one MS, it is specified that head space is supposed to be considered sufficient if the animals can stand in a natural position, whereas the guidelines from another MS are based on recommendations from SCAHAW (2002) and specifies that the distance from the highest point on pigs should be at least 15 cm if the vehicle is supplied with mechanical ventilation and 30 cm if it is only naturally ventilated. Recently, in a study involving weaners of 20-25 kg, variation in the deck height between 41-111% of body height were shown to have only insignificant and sporadic effects on indicators of ventilation and of natural movements during 23h journeys in trucks of 4 or 5 decks holding animals at commercial density (Herskin et al., 2022).

4.2 The means of transport

Not only the indicators related to the animals, but also indicators related to the means of transport can be difficult to assess in a roadside inspection. One example is the drinkers, the design of which is supposed to be appropriate for the category of animals. As reported by EFSA (EFSA AHAW Panel et al., 2022), no studies have examined how much water pigs drink during transport. It is often seen that water tanks are emptied, but how much is wasted and how the water intake is distributed among individuals on the same deck is not known. In addition, the inspector will not know what type of drinker the pigs in a given vehicle have been used to while on farm, and thus cannot know if the animals are familiar with the type in the vehicle.

One part of the inspection of the means of transport known to be a challenge is the assessment of in-vehicle temperature. In some of the guidelines made available to EURCAW, it is explained how appropriate position of sensors should be interpreted (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Illustration of appropriate placing of temperature sensors in multideck livestock vehicles, obtained from the guidelines for roadside inspection in one MS.

It is, however, not mentioned where in the vehicle the temperatures and/or the output from sensors should be checked. In the check lists in some MSs, the inspector has to tick 'YES', 'NO' or 'N/A' for the assessment of temperatures, whereas in another example the inspector should tick 'YES', 'NO', 'NOT INSPECTED' or 'NA'. In addition to this variability and the uncertainty as to where the actual temperature should be measured in the vehicle under inspection, recent data from Chen et al. (under review) showed quite large differences between temperatures measured by sensors situated in the wall of a Type II vehicle used to transport weaners on 4-5 decks and temperature measured in the centre of the vehicle, just next to the pigs. Thus, with the current placing of sensors along the periphery of vehicles, the quantified temperatures are probably quite lower than what the animals experience in the centre of vehicles.

5 Conclusions

This report was based on input from four EU MS's as well as secondary input from two others. The input varied in terms of quality and length and involved both guidelines and check-lists for roadside inspections of animal welfare during transport or only one of these. The focus has been on journeys lasting more than 8 hours, where water should be provided to pigs during transport. The input received from MS's as well as scientific and other literature have been used to create an overview of the checklists used for roadside inspection of animal welfare as well as the reporting of these data. In short, the checklists are mainly based on the wording from EC Regulation 1/2005, however with some variation. In the reporting, it is most often not possible to identify results of checks of vehicles along a roadside versus checks at for example assembly barns, control posts, or slaughterhouses. The report highlights the challenges that inspectors encounter during roadside checks (see Mc Loughlin 2023). Further study is required to understand how inspectors navigate the challenges of roadside inspection.

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EURCAW-Pigs is the first European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare. It focuses on pig welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle of pigs from birth to the end of life. EURCAW-Pigs' main objective is a harmonised compliance with EU legislation regarding welfare in EU Member States. This includes:

- for pig husbandry: Directives 98/58/EC and 2008/120/EC;
- for pig transport: Regulation (EC) No 1/2005;
- for slaughter and killing of pigs: Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009.

EURCAW-Pigs supports:

- inspectors of Competent Authorities (CA's);
- pig welfare policy workers;
- bodies supporting CA's with science, training, and communication.

Website and contact

EURCAW-Pigs' website www.eurcaw-pigs.eu offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of pig welfare legislation.

Are you an inspector or pig welfare policy worker, or otherwise dealing with advice or support for official controls of pig welfare? Your question is our challenge! Please, send us an email with your question and details and we'll get you in touch with the right expert.

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